

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton

TELEMEDICINE AS A TOOL TO MANAGE POORLY CONTROLLED TYPE 2 DIABETES
MELLITUS: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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By

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes has become an increasing problem throughout the years. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services and other insurance payers financially incentivize providers for maintaining diabetes control measures. Telemedicine has been shown to be effective in managing diabetic patients. The aim of this project is to improve outcomes for patients with poorly controlled diabetic mellitus (PCDM) type 2, by utilizing telemedicine as a tool. The purpose of the project was to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to usual care for PCDM patients at an outpatient clinic. The quality improvement (QI) project took place at an outpatient clinic. Inclusion criteria: 25 patients who had a visit in the previous two months prior to the project initiation, ages 40-65, English or Spanish speaking and a diagnosis of PCDM. The independent variable was telemedicine. The dependent variables were A1C values and patient monthly logs, i.e. medication, diet, exercise, and fasting blood glucose (FBG). A baseline A1C was collected in August 2020, November 2020 (first benchmark), and February 2021(second benchmark). Telemedicine visits were in December 2020 and January 2021. There were 12 patients out of 25 patients that were included in the results for A1C because any patient that did not follow up with A1C lab was excluded from the A1C results. The A1C value decreased in 9 out of 12 patients (75%) who had their A1C lab results after the first benchmark however, it was noted that in the second benchmark, 8 out 12 patients (67%) had a decrease in A1C. Telemedicine appeared to be an effective tool when added to usual care in managing patients with PCDM however a continuation of telemedicine is recommended since the COVID-19 surges could have impacted the results.

Keywords: Telemedicine, diabetes mellitus, poor control diabetes

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Background

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2020) reports that 34.2 million Americans aged 18 years or older have Diabetes Mellitus (DM). The number of patients with DM continues to rise, with an incidence of 1.5 million US adults per year (CDC, 2020). According to The American Diabetes Association, Diabetes was the seventh leading cause of death in the United States in 2017, totaling 83,564 death certificates that diabetes was the underlying cause of death (ADA, 2020). The American Diabetes Association (ADA, 2018) estimates the annual cost of diabetes in the US to be \$327 billion, an increase of 26% from 2012 to 2017 (ADA, 2018). In 2017, DM patients had medical expenses 2.3 times higher than those without DM and data remained consistent from 2007 to 2012 (ADA, 2018). *The Healthy People 2020* diabetes' goal is to reduce the disease and its economic burden, as well as to improve the quality of life of people with or at risk for diabetes (DHS, 2020).

McCoy et al. (2016) suggest that providers' quality improvement (QI) of DM is contingent on accurately measuring and reporting current performance regarding treatment. Furthermore, metrics such as the glycosylated hemoglobin (A1C) blood test level < 8.0 are currently patient outcomes to incentivize providers for pay-for-performance reimbursement and public reporting. These standards are from the Healthcare Effectiveness Data and Information Set (HEDIS), measures developed by the National Committee for Quality Assurance (NCQA) (McCoy et al., 2016). The DNP project clinic identified a significant number of patients diagnosed with Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 (DMT2) with an A1C level >7 , indicating poor control. Innovative interventions are required to improve outcomes among DMT2 patients who are nonresponsive or noncompliant with usual care (Crowley et al., 2014; McLendon, 2017.)

Lee et.al., (2017) investigated the impact of different telemedicine strategies on glycemic

control management on patients with DMT2. The main telemedicine intervention was via telephone including study elements of behavioral therapy and educational counseling. The results showed that teleconsultation was the most effective telemedicine strategy followed by telemonitoring plus case management. Telemedicine as a tool to manage DMT2 has proven to be more effective than the usual care in managing diabetes (Tchero et al., 2019; McLendon, 2017). Telemedicine (also referred to as "telehealth" or "e-health") has been an effective means for health care professionals to evaluate, diagnose and treat patients in remote locations using telecommunications technology (AMD, 2019). The Health Resources & Services Administration (HRSA) defines telehealth as the use of electronic information and telecommunication technologies support and promote long-distance clinical health care, patient and professional health-related education, public health, and health administration. Technologies include videoconferencing, internet, store-and-forward imaging, streaming media, and terrestrial and wireless communication. Telemedicine refers specifically to remote clinical services, whereas telehealth refers to remote non-direct patient care services, such as provider training, administrative meetings, and continuing medical education, in addition to clinical services (DHHS, n.d.). Concurrently, as a response to the nationwide Coronavirus pandemic, the clinic found it necessary to explore alternative treatment opportunities that supported CDC recommendations for quarantine and social distancing.

Problem Statement

This QI project will aim at improving outcomes for poorly controlled (PCDM) patients by utilizing telemedicine as a tool. The Model for Improvement (MI) will be the framework used to guide the DNP project. QI projects allow clinicians, working within a team, to identify an issue and implement interventions that can result in measurable improvements in care (Jones et

al., 2019). Furthermore, engagement in QI enables clinicians to acquire, assimilate, and apply important professional skills that address longstanding concerns and improve population health in specific areas of study, such as the DMT2 patient populace (Jones, 2019).

At the project facility, patients identified with PCDM often have a history of missed primary care follow up appointments, lack of adherence to medication, high carbohydrate intake, limited or no exercise and lack of education. Additionally, the DNP project clinic site received a report from a major (independent IPA) insurance carrier, showing below standard performance for DM control (40%). Substandard care can result in further deterioration of health, inefficient utilization of healthcare systems, poor patient care flow and decreased quality of life (Li, 2019). The problem this QI project addresses is the need to improve PCDM outcomes for patients by utilizing telemedicine as a tool.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this QI project is to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to usual care for PCDM patients at an outpatient clinic.

Supporting Framework

The framework to be used for supporting the QI project is the Model for Improvement (MI) developed by the Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI). The MI is an approach that has shown to accelerate effective and efficient improvements rooted in Total Quality Management (TQM). TQM is a system of management known for inclusion of all staff in problem-solving, and Rapid Cycle Improvements (RCI) (Langley et al., 2009). The MI has been used in a variety of healthcare settings across hundreds of organizations (Langley, 2009). The MI was developed out of W. Edward Deming's work that integrated management principles with increased quality and cost reduction strategies to create positive change (Langley, 2009). The MI

is a two-part method, the first part includes three fundamental questions and the second part has Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA) cycles (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Model for Improvement

Note. Based on information from (Langley, 2009).

Question 1 (Q1) defines the aim of the project, specific to the population of interest, the timeframe in which the project will take place and how the intervention will be measured.

Question 2 (Q2) the QI team uses quantitative measures to determine if a specific change actually led to an improvement in practices. Question 3 (Q3) asks, what change can we make that will result in improvement? (Langley, 2009). This question refers to the identification of a problem and the recognition for the need for improvement.

The PDSA cycles, which guide the tests for change determine if the changes made have resulted in an improvement (Langley, 2009). The PDSA cycle tests a change by planning it, trying it, observing the results, and acting on what was learned (Langley, 2009).

The first step is to *Plan*. Planning involves testing or observing the change. It includes a plan for collecting data stating the objective of the test, making predictions about what will happen and why, and developing a plan to test the change. During the plan step, the individuals who need to be evaluated are identified. The change or intervention that will be used to address the identified problem or aim is recognized and the timeframe and location in which the project will take place is established. Lastly, the data is identified to evaluate the intervention.

Step two is *Do*. This step involves testing the intervention on a small scale. During this step, problems with the intervention and unexpected observations are documented. It is at this point that data analysis begins.

The third step is *Study*. During this step, time is set aside to analyze the data and study the results. Once the data analysis is completed, the results are compared to previous predictions. The results are summarized, and then the information is evaluated for what was learned and how the intervention led to practice change.

Act is step four, which involves refining the change based on the results. The team determines if the intervention created a change or if a modification to the intervention is needed. If the intervention created an improvement, then no additional PDSA cycles are required. If the team identified that the intervention did not address the problem, then modification to the intervention should occur with another PDSA cycle being conducted to evaluate the change.

The integration of the MI and project steps were as follows: The DNP project utilized the MI to improve management of PCDM patients. The team consisted of a Family Nurse Practitioner (FNP), the lead care coordinator (CC), a medical assistant, and the office manager. The FNP was the project author for the QI project. The team members integrated the MI into the project by first answering the three fundamental questions. According to the IHI, the answers to the questions were the project's aims; Q1- What were we trying to accomplish? The aim was to improve A1C values for PCDM patients within a six-month period by using telemedicine services in addition to usual care. Q2 - How did we know that a change was an improvement? To fulfill this aim, the team analyzed the A1C values at baseline, November 2020 and February 2021 and the patient care logs for corresponding monthly medication compliance, diet (carbohydrate intake), exercise and self-monitoring fasting blood glucose (SMFBG) average. The team marked A1C results and patient monthly log data on an excel spreadsheet as follows:

1. Medication compliance was marked by putting a one value for compliant with diabetic medication and a two value for noncompliant for the corresponding month.
2. Diet, a one value was marked if the daily carbohydrate intake was less than 40% and a two value if the daily carbohydrate intake was over 40%.
3. Exercise, a one value was marked if the patient met 150 minutes a week of walking exercise and a two value if was not met.

4. FBG, a one value was marked if the patient had an average SMFBG of equal to or less than 130 and a two value of over 130 for the corresponding month.

Q3 -What change was made that resulted in an improvement? This aim was the proposed change to address PCDM using telemedicine to provide on-going care through continuous monitoring.

Aligning and sequencing the project's action steps within the PDSA steps was the second part of the MI. During the first stage *Plan*, the team was gathered to delineate roles and responsibilities. The team consisted of a provider (FNP), a care coordinator, a medical assistant, and the office manager. The team planned the telemedicine appointments and the data required for collection and method on how it was going to be collected. The data collection included the laboratory test of A1C and patient monthly logs (medication, diet, exercise and FBG). The team predicted that the A1C value would decrease due to the use of telemedicine visits. The patient population consisted of PCDM patients, who were provided two consecutive monthly appointments via telemedicine. The usual care is that patients with DM3 are seen every three months when their A1C value shows poor control (>7) and every six months when their diabetes is well controlled (<7). The location in which the project will take place is located in an outpatient clinic in Norwalk, California.

During the *Do* step, the project author evaluated the use of telemedicine visits on a small scale to address PCDM patients. Patients were identified through an electronic medical record (EMR) system to determine PCDM. Once identified, 25 patients who met the eligible criteria were scheduled for an appointment in August 2020 to discuss the Diabetes Action Plan (DAP) (Appendix A) including baseline A1C value. The DAP was developed, based on the Health Net Federal Services, Tricare (2017) template. Patients then had their A1C blood test in November

and had a telemedicine visit in December 2020 to discuss their A1C value and patient care logs significance and recommended adjustments. The patients had an additional telemedicine visit in January 2021 to discuss their updated patient logs and the adjustments that were made. The final visit was in February to discuss updated A1C value and patient advised adjustments. The project author then gathered the data (A1C values and patient logs) and transferred data to an excel spreadsheet.

In step three, *Study*, the project author set aside time to analyze the results and made a comparison with the predicted outcomes. The project author summarized the findings and determined that some changes were required with further refinement on some of the patients.

The last step is *Act*. In this step, the project author refined the changes, if required. Changes were made based on what was learned from the intervention. If changes were required, a repetition of the PDSA cycle was modified until the desired results were achieved or the until the project was abandoned. If the change was an improvement, then the data was presented to the clinic owner to propose continuation of the implementation of telemedicine for the treatment of PCDM patients.

Review of Literature

A review of literature was conducted to support the DNP project for evaluating telemedicine as a tool to better manage DMT2 patients. The databases used included PubMed, CINAHL and Google Scholar. The literature search consisted of key terms DM, PCDM, and uncontrolled DM. Additional terms included DM management, telemedicine, and telehealth. Articles were selected if they were written in English, peer reviewed and published from 2014 to 2020. No editorials, case reports or project descriptions were selected. The articles included adults over age 18. The articles selected included Randomized Control Trials (RCT) and systematic reviews with meta-analysis. The following topics were used to organize the review of literature: DMT2 pathophysiology, DM complications, DM management concerns, and telemedicine.

Pathophysiology

In DMT2, various genetic and environmental factors can result in the progressive loss of β -cell mass and/or function that manifests clinically as hyperglycemia (ADA, 2020). Patients with all forms of diabetes are at risk for developing the same chronic complications; however, progression rates may differ. DMT2 is associated with insulin secretory defects related to inflammation and metabolic stress, which also includes genetic factors. Furthermore, a deficient β -cell insulin secretion, frequently associated with insulin resistance, appears to be the common factor in developing DMT2 (ADA, 2020). According to the ADA, (2020) patients with DMT2 have defective and insufficient insulin secretion and are unable to compensate for their insulin resistance. Insulin resistance may improve with weight reduction and/or pharmacologic treatment of hyperglycemia (Goswami, et al., 2014).

Diabetes Mellitus Complication Issues

Diabetics are at an increased risk for numerous health complications and development of chronic conditions resulting in higher rates of morbidity and mortality. Prolonged uncontrolled DM progresses into a broad range of macrovascular complications such as heart and vascular disease leading to myocardial infarction and transient ischemic attacks secondary to accelerated atherosclerosis from glucose-induced oxidative stress (Fowler, 2008). Additionally, microvascular complications can cause neuropathy, kidney failure and diabetic retinopathy (leading to blindness) (Papatheodorou et al., 2018).

Diabetes Mellitus Management Issues

At least 45% of patients with DMT2 fail to achieve adequate glycemic control (Polonsky & Henry, 2016). Several factors contribute to poor glycemic control (>7 Hb A1c) including patient adherence to self-care recommendations such as medication adherence, high carbohydrate diet (>40 percent of daily intake) and lack of exercise (Polonsky and Henry, 2016). Some management challenges for patient lifestyle modification changes included low health literacy, difficulty in changing established behavioral habits, and perceived lack of symptoms. Other key factors are patient demographics such as limited education, low-income, patient beliefs about self-care recommendations (e.g., perceived treatment inefficacy), and perceived patient burden regarding obtaining and taking their medications, e.g., treatment complexity, out-of-pocket costs, and hypoglycemia (Polonsky & Henry, 2016).

Additionally, multiple studies identified a consistent lack of integrated care in many health care systems and clinical inertia among health care providers (Polonsky and Henry, 2016; Egede et al., 2014). Whittemore et al. (2019) conducted a study identifying the challenges faced by patients and healthcare providers regarding DMT2 management. The results showed that

personal challenges included cultural beliefs, lack of resources, challenges to lifestyle modification, lack of family support/competing demands, and mental health issues. System level challenges included lack of resources, perceived quality of care, and limited patient engagement (Whittemore et al., 2019). Healthcare providers and patients have different perceptions about the causation and treatment for DMT2, which results in treatment conflict. While some adults with DMT2 understood that genetics and lifestyle contributed to the development of DMT2, others lacked understanding of these contributory factors (Whittemore et al., 2019). Healthcare providers benefit from screening their patients for their understanding of diabetes and cultural beliefs in managing their DMT2.

Healthcare providers are also challenged with time constraints and a lack of access to resources, i.e., diabetes self-management educational programs, nutrition, case management or exercise programs (Whittemore et al., 2019). Fragmented care is often the result of limited access to specialized diabetes management, education programs and suboptimal referral systems, which account for the high prevalence of PCDM mismanagement (ADA, 2019).

Some healthcare system challenges discussed in literature that were identified between the provider and patients with PCDM patients included clinic resources and quality of care, staff insensitivity and patient engagement barriers (Whittemore et al., 2019). These challenges can be addressed by the addition of innovative evidence-based interventions, e.g., telemedicine), which have been proven to be more effective than clinic-based care (Crowley et al., 2014). For example, telemedicine with continuous monitoring can provide an A1C value for the provider resulting in appropriate follow up patient guidance. Furthermore, telemedicine provides improved access for patients which often increases patient engagement. Given the significant

complications associated with elevated A1C values, it is imperative for providers to recognize them and provide appropriate monitoring and treatment for PCDM.

Usual Care/Standard Guidelines

Currently, in the DNP project clinic, usual care is consistent with the ADA treatment guidelines in Appendix B (ADA, 2019). The lifestyle modifications more specifically include exercising at least 150 minutes a week (Colberg et al., 2016) and eating a well-balanced 1800 calorie diet with less than 40 percent carbohydrates (Gray & Threlkeld, 2019).

In addition, the DNP project clinic follows the American Diabetes Association testing guidelines. The ADA defines well-controlled DM by the A1C value $< 7\%$. Thus, patients at the with a history of A1C $< 7\%$ are evaluated every six months, and $\geq 7\%$ are evaluated every three months (ADA, 2020). Self-Monitoring Blood Glucose depends on the instrument and user; therefore, it is important for the provider to evaluate each patient appropriately in order to ensure that the data used is effective and timely (ADA, 2020). Additional laboratory for fasting lipid, urine microalbumin/creatinine ratio, and a retinal eye and foot exam are checked annually (ADA, 2019).

At the project site, usual care also includes referring a patient to an endocrinologist if the provider is unable to stabilize the A1C value or the patient is non-compliant. Achieving A1C targets of seven or below (53 mmol/mol) has been shown to reduce complications of diabetes (ADA, 2018). Epidemiologic analyses demonstrated a curvilinear relationship between A1C and microvascular complications, suggesting that the greatest number of complications will be averted by taking patients from very poor control to fair/good control (Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT), 1993; United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS), 1998). Studies also indicated that for each percent reduction in A1C, there was a corresponding

14 percent reduction in myocardial infarction, 12 percent reduction in stroke, and a 37 percent reduction of microvascular complications (Stratton et al., 2000).

Telemedicine

Telemedicine has been proven to be effective in improving DMT2 outcomes (Faruque et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2017; McLendon, 2017; Tchero et al., 2018; & Wu et al., 2018).

Telemedicine's effectiveness in the management of DMT2 has been studied extensively. The majority of studies included in the literature review were systematic reviews with meta-analysis. The study participants were all adults with DMT2. Various types of telemedicine interventions were used in studies (telehealth, telecare, telemonitoring, teleconsultation) either synchronous or asynchronous.

Faruque et al., (2017); Tchero et al., (2018), and Wu et al., (2018) conducted systematic reviews with meta-analysis comparing telemedicine with usual care and found that telemedicine was effective, either when added to usual care or telemedicine in the replacement of usual care for improving DMT2 outcomes. Faruque, et al. (2017) focused on various types of telemedicine interventions such as telehealth (clinical services provided at a distance) and telemonitoring (remote collection and transmission of clinical data from patients to providers). The authors concluded that the addition of telemedicine, especially systems that allowed medication adjustments improved A1C values. Tchero et al. (2018) showed that telemonitoring interventions are more effective than usual care in managing diabetes, especially for DMT2 patients. The mean reduction in A1C was significantly higher in the telemedicine groups ($p < 0.001$).

Wu et al. (2018) focused on tele-education, telemonitoring, teleconsultation, telecase management, and telementoring. The length of the studies ranged from 6-12 months. Most trials involved SMFBG and weekly data submission using mobile phone, telephone, or internet.

Feedback included advice regarding medication, diet and physical activity. The authors found that telehealth was more effective than usual care in controlling the glycemic index in patients with diabetes ($P < .001$).

The types of telemedicine that were most effective were telemonitoring with clinical feedback or communication from providers using some technology or device with a healthcare system that allowed for medication adjustments (Faruque et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2017; Tchero et al., 2018 & Wu et al., 2018). Faruque et al.'s (2017) studies focused primarily on trials in which patients received clinical communication from providers using some technology or devices. Findings showed that in addition to telemedicine, systems that allowed medication adjustments with or without text messaging or a Web portal, improved A1C.

In an RCT by Greenwood et al. (2015), an evaluation of a telehealth remote monitoring intervention using paired glucose testing and asynchronous data analysis in adults with DM2 established a DM program with telephonic nurse care coordination for DM population health management. The intervention measured the effects of A1C compared to usual care over 6 months. The results showed a significant change in A1C ($P < .005$). The authors concluded that an eHealth model, incorporating a complete feedback loop with telehealth remote monitoring and paired glucose testing with asynchronous data analysis, significantly improved A1C levels compared to usual care.

In summary, there is cumulative evidence that telemedicine is effective in the management of DM. The evidence is powerful and from reputable sources to make a claim that telemedicine is effective in the reduction of A1C value, which translates into better DM control. Systematic reviews are considered the highest level of evidence (Polit & Beck, 2012). The

review of literature supports the QI project to introduce telemedicine into clinical practice to treat and manage PCDM patients.

Methods

The methods section includes information about the design, setting, sample, ethical considerations, variables, planning, and evaluation.

Plan/Design

The design was a quality improvement project guided by the IHI Model for Improvement, whose interventional steps were aligned with the PDSA cycle (Figure 1). The PDSA was selected for its evidence in accelerating improvements. This design was developed to successfully fulfill the purpose of the project to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to standard care for PCDM patients at a primary outpatient clinic. The project used evidence-based strategies, expert opinion, and ethical considerations to improve the clinical care and outcomes of PCDM patients.

Setting

The QI project took place at a private outpatient clinic located in Norwalk, California. The clinic serves mainly adults who are low to middle income. The clinic provides preventative care along with the treatment for acute and chronic conditions. The clinic has one physician, one family nurse practitioner (QI project author), one clinic manager, one care coordinator, and two medical assistants. The clinic serves a predominately Latino/ Spanish speaking community and the entire clinic staff speaks Spanish. The clinic is open Monday through Friday, 8:30 am to 5:00 pm. Twenty-five percent of the clinic population was diagnosed with DM. The clinic accepts Medicaid, Medicare, and private insurance as well as cash.

Sample

The project consisted of 25 patients who were diagnosed with PCDM. The inclusion criteria consisted of established patients who were seen at least once in the last two months prior

to the project initiation, adults between the ages of 40 to 65, English or Spanish speaking and diagnosed with PCDM. Exclusion criteria consisted of patients with patients with Type one Diabetes Mellitus, gestational DM or patients with mental impairments of any type. The patients were identified using the Electronic Medical Record (EMR) to address the query for patients who met the inclusion criteria. Patients were identified via coding criteria for PCDM within the problem list section in the EMR.

Ethical Considerations

Approval for the QI project was granted by the clinical director of the project facility (Appendix C). The project was submitted to the Internal Review Board at California State University, Fullerton and was approved. Participants provided verbal consent after a participant script was read (Appendix D). Patient privacy was protected using numerical values, in order that the data was not connected to patient identifying information. This was done to ensure we are compliant with the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act for each patient. Data was maintained on a password protected computer in which only the project author had access.

Variables

The independent variable was telemedicine. Telemedicine was provided to patients identified as having PCDM. The dependent variables (quality indicators) were Hgb A1C, and patient monthly logs for medication compliance, diet (\leq or $>$ 40% carbohydrate intake), exercise (\leq or $>$ 150 minutes per week), and average SMFBG.

The data was entered into the electronic medical record (EMR) visit and on the EXCEL spreadsheet with patient identifiers. The levels were documented in the patient's blood glucose monthly log. Patients maintained daily exercise and diet logs to document their physical activity, and food and beverage consumption for monthly review.

Planning

This project utilized the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) framework as outlined by the IHI Model for Improvement processes. The *Plan* step involved the project author providing an overview of the project, which included a project timeline (Figure 2) for the clinic staff to support implementation of the interventions. A project overview was given through a PowerPoint presentation. Project implementation occurred August 2020 through February of 2021. During this timeframe, each patient was given a diabetic action plan during their telemedicine visit (Appendix A). The patients were put on the schedule as a 10-minute consented telemedicine visit. A telemedicine patient visits included EMR documentation using a smart phrase template as shown in Appendix E. Smart phrases were used to identify the quality indicators taken during each visit. This information helped to predict maintenance of care and/or alterations of future care plans. A PDSA cycle diagram was created (Figure 1).

Figure 2

Project Timeline

The *Do* step was the implementation of the intervention, which involved an EMR query conducted to obtain baseline data in August 2020. The data included name (changed to a numerical value for privacy), age and baseline A1C levels prior to the implementation of telemedicine intervention. Additional data retrieved included A1C levels in November 2020 and February 2021 during the implementation phase of telemedicine. The project author consulted with patients via telemedicine using telephone virtual check-ins for the months of December 2020 and January 2021. Patient logs (status on medication, diet, exercise and SMFBG), were reviewed via telemedicine and patients were counseled based on the data (A1C values' logs).

Evaluation

The *Study* step included a patient chart review by the project author for data which was included in the data Excel spreadsheet. The data was compared for pre- and post-intervention. The data was reviewed and analyzed for changes in the quality indicators (A1C and patient logs) compared to the baseline data. Quality indicators were displayed using a bar graph to show data comparisons. The team discussed the challenges to implement the intervention and identify areas for continuous improvement.

Results

The purpose of this QI project was to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to usual care for PCDM patients at an outpatient clinic. The A1C results are displayed in Figure 3 and the patient log results in Figure 2. There were 12 patients out of 25 patients that were included in the results for A1C because any patient that did not follow up with A1C lab was excluded from the A1C results. The patients that did not follow up with lab all reported an issue related to Covid pandemic surge, such as limited appointments available in laboratories or patient fears of going out and contracting the virus. The A1C value decreased in 9 out of 12 patients (75%) who had their A1C lab results after the first benchmark however, it was noted that in the second benchmark, 8 out of 12 patients (67%) had a decrease in A1C. The second benchmark, is where most of the patients did not follow up with lab orders. There were two patients who confirmed that they were regularly seen by an endocrinologist specialist however admitted lack of follow up. One patient linked to endocrine had a slight increase in their A1C value (A1C of 9.7 at the first benchmark and A1C of 9.8 during the second benchmark).

Figure 3

A1c Values

Note. A1c values ranging from 5.0 to 11.0. The results at baseline (August, 2020) and quarterly consecutively.

Furthermore, the clinic's procedure referral follow-up process was not clear and there were noted inconsistencies with insurance coverage, especially for referrals to nutrition/certified diabetic educator. Patient logs results were graphed in Figure 4. Medication non-compliance decreased from the first to second benchmark from 40% to 28% indicating that the telemedicine visits were effective. Many patients admitted to having trouble understanding how their diabetic medication should be taken. These patients received additional education during their telemedicine visit. In addition, all but one of the patients were Latino and noted that many engaged in alternative health practices which negatively impacted medication compliance. One patient reported eating bird seeds as an alternate to DM medication. However, after some counseling with these patients, there was a noted increase in medication understanding and compliance, suggesting telemedicine may have been effective.

There appeared to be a correlation between higher A1C levels and those patients whose diets consisted of over 40% daily carbohydrate intake. Patients overall had a hard time in controlling carbohydrates intake and were consuming over 40% carbohydrates in their diet. The patients consuming more than 40% of carbohydrates from their diet after telemedicine visits decreased from 76% to 60% from the first to second benchmark. Many patients admitted to an awareness of a high carbohydrate diet; however, they struggled with carbohydrate cravings, limited access to healthy food, limited financial resources and time constraints. During counseling there was a discussion of options such as meal prepping or food substitutions (Figure 4).

Figure 4*Patient Monthly Logs*

Note. Percentage of patient monthly logs at the first benchmark (December , 2020) and the second benchmark (January, 2021).

Exercise appeared to be a struggle for most patients. Many patients reported lack of motivation due to fear of Covid pandemic. Patients exercising more than 150 minutes per week increased from eight at the first benchmark to twelve percent at the second benchmark. Patients with a daily average SMFBG ≤ 130 after the first benchmark increased from 36% to 60% after telemedicine visits. However, some patients showed inconsistencies with their FBG and their A1C value.

Limitations

The project had several limitations. One limitation was that the COVID-19 pandemic interfered with the patients' abilities to receive follow-up care with laboratory and specialty referrals. Many patients reported office closures or difficulty scheduling appointments due to the COVID-19 surge. Another limitation was the absence of telemedicine policy/procedures.

Discussion

The results were consistent with the literature in that telemedicine was an effective tool to manage patients with poorly controlled diabetes in an outpatient clinical setting. There was a noted change in all measures, specifically an increase in medication compliance, a decrease in patient consumption of daily carbohydrate intake > 40%, and a decrease in SMFBG > 130, resulting in an improvement in A1C values among patients with PCDM at the second benchmark. The types of telemedicine visits that were most effective were consistent with the literature which were telemonitoring with communication from providers using technology or a device with a healthcare system that allowed for medication adjustments (Faruque et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2017; Tchero et al., 2018; & Wu et al., 2018).

Also noted some of the challenges this population faced that were mirrored in the literature, such as lack of resources, lifestyle modification challenges and the perceived patient experience of healthcare management by the provider (Polonsky & Henry, 2016 & Egede et al., 2014). For example, I had several patients that stated that they had limited money to buy healthy food and others who felt that they could not afford gym memberships. In addition, most patients had limited education on meal prepping. Many patients complained about feeling unmotivated to exercise and closure to most centers such as the gym created an increased barrier to exercise.

Furthermore, the project results were consistent with patient factors known to contribute to PCDM related to self-care recommendations, such as medication adherence, high carbohydrate diet (>40 percent of daily intake) and lack of exercise (Polonsky & Henry, 2016). Diet and exercise were the most challenging factors patients faced. Many patients consumed over 40 percent of carbohydrates daily intake. For example, a typical Latino patient consumes 6-10 tortillas in a day and required multiple conversations to wean off the tortillas. Additionally,

patients struggled to meet the exercise recommendation of 150 minutes per week. The majority of the patients reported they were too tired from work or lacked access to parks and gyms. Many of the gyms and parks were closed due to COVID 19 situation. Some healthcare system challenges discussed in literature that were identified between the provider and patients with PCDM patients included clinic resources and quality of care, staff insensitivity and patient engagement barriers (Whittemore et al., 2019). This was consistent with the QI project which noted a gap in the referral process to nutrition/CDE. In addition, I noticed some patient frustrations which resulted in multiple complaints of staff being rude. We had a high turnover rate of staffing due to COVID 19 and were challenged to meet the patient customer satisfaction requirement especially for this population who many times are feeling irritated as part of their disease process.

Furthermore, patient engagement barriers were prominent because so many patients lacked follow up with getting their A1C labs drawn. The COVID-19 pandemic surge resulted in limited lab availability appointment and patient fears of transmission.

Recommendations

Based on the QI results, telemedicine appeared to be promising in the management of poorly controlled PCDM patients. Poorly controlled patients with diabetes could benefit from continuous telemedicine monitoring with some form of integration of electronic systems that will enable more frequent monitoring. Poorly controlled diabetic patients could benefit from monthly telemedicine visits until patient reaches the recommended value of A1C (<7) and then resume usual care.

Furthermore, communication with referrals that were ordered, such as endocrine and

nutrition, should be enhanced. In addition, the education processes related to diabetes self-management education (DSME) and behavioral modifications (motivational interviewing) should be part of the telehealth visit. Patient education programs such as DSME have been shown to reduce morbidity and mortality related to DMT2 (McLendon, 2017). Regarding FBG monitoring, there should be an integrated system where SMFBG levels are sent directly to the provider electronically. Another recommendation is to integrate a system that will allow for texting or use of a web portal to support PCDM patient access. Lastly, implementing telemedicine policies and procedures would be beneficial for clinic staff.

Conclusion

As the incidence of diabetes increases, improved access to diabetes care is necessary. Telemedicine has been shown in the literature and in this QI project to be an effective tool to improve access and manage PCDM. Despite the Coronavirus's detrimental impact on the nation, this project demonstrated the benefits of an alternative care practice compared to usual care for PCDM patients. The project's positive results justify continued use of telemedicine combined with usual care as an effective model to support PCDM patients in self-managing diabetes.

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APPENDIX A

Diabetes Action Plan

Diabetes Action Plan

This **action plan** is a guide to help you manage the signs and symptoms of diabetes. You and your provider should complete this plan together at your next visit. The three colors (zones), green, yellow and red, help you decide what to do.

Zone	Status	Symptoms	Actions
GREEN	<p>Green means you are doing well. Symptoms are STABLE.</p> <p>Your diabetes is well controlled.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • normal blood glucose levels • blood glucose level between 80 and 130, or _____ before a meal • blood glucose level less than 180 or _____ two hours after a meal • no illness – cold, flu, infection • stress is controlled • feeling good 	<p>Continue the basic four:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor blood glucose. • Take medications. • Follow a balanced diet. • Exercise regularly.
YELLOW	<p>Yellow means CAUTION.</p> <p>Your symptoms indicate you may need to talk with your provider.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • random high blood glucose – over 200 or _____ • elevated blood glucose at same time of day for three days in a five-day period • frequent low blood glucose – less than 70 or _____ • symptoms of acute illness • stress not controlled • feeling tired, depressed • lacking energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check blood glucose more often. • Treat high or low blood glucose levels with treatment options from reverse side. • Call your provider if you have repeated patterns of highs and lows, or if symptoms persist.
RED	<p>Red means you may need help IMMEDIATELY! Symptoms are unstable.</p> <p>You need to be evaluated now if your yellow zone actions have not helped your symptoms improve.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • blood glucose at 300 or higher for two tests in a row or _____ • positive urine ketones • confusion • fruity breath • difficulty breathing • nausea • vomiting • diarrhea • dehydration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Call your provider. • Refer to sick plan on back of this page.

Note. Adapted from Health Net Federal Services.

(<https://www.hnfs.com/content/dam/hnfs/tw/common/pdf/WellnessProgramMaterials/Diabetes/PF1113x030>). Copyright 2017. From Tricare.

APPENDIX B

American Diabetes Association Treatment Guidelines

Note. This figure was produced by the 2021 ADA Professional Practice Committee to outline glucose-lowering medication in type 2 diabetes and was adapted by Davies MJ, D'Alessio DA, Fradkin J. Diabetes Care 2018;41: 2669–2701.

APPENDIX C

Facility Approval Letter by Clinical Director

Date: March 03, 2020

To: Dr. Daniel Uribe M.D.
Norwalk, Ca 90650

13307 San Antonio Drive

From: Alicia Calzada, FNP-C

Re: Doctorate of Nursing Practice Project

As part of the Doctorate of Nursing Practice, candidates complete a culminating project. A synopsis of my project follows: **Background:** Diabetes has become such a problem throughout the years that not only national goals have had to be created but has been recognized by CMS and other insurance payers who will financially incentivize providers (pay-for-performance) for maintaining diabetes control measured through A1C values. Despite these efforts, diabetes continues to be a problem and we see it firsthand in the clinic. A noted trend among diabetics with poor diabetes control is that they have a history of missed office visits. In addition, our clinic recently had a review with one of our main IPAs to show areas for clinic opportunity and noted that our diabetics had substandard results based on A1C values. According to the research, Telemedicine has been shown to be effective in managing diabetic patients. With COVID-19 pandemic and social distancing/isolation requirements, our clinic had no other choice but to start managing patients via telemedicine. **Aim:** This Quality Improvement (QI) project will aim at improving outcomes for poorly controlled (PCDM) patients by utilizing telemedicine as a tool. Quality Improvement projects allow clinicians, working within a team, to identify an issue and implement interventions that can result in measurable improvements in care (Jones, 2019). **Purpose:** The purpose of this QI project is to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to usual care for PCDM patients at an outpatient clinic. **Methods:** This design was developed to successfully fulfill the purpose to evaluate the effectiveness of adding telemedicine to standard care for PCDM patients at a primary outpatient clinic. The project was planned to use evidenced based strategies, expert opinion, and ethical considerations to improve the clinical care and outcomes of PCDM patients. The project team will include a family nurse practitioner (project author), medical assistant, office manager). The project will include 25 patients who have been diagnosed with PCDM. The inclusion criteria will consist of established patients who were seen at least once in the last two months prior to the project initiation, adults between the ages of 40-65, English or Spanish speaking and have a diagnosis of PCDM. The independent variable is the

telemedicine that will be provided to patients identified as having PCDM. The dependent variables are Hgb A1C, and patient monthly logs (FBG, Diet, and Exercise). Fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels will be checked before breakfast. The FBG levels will be documented into the patient's blood glucose monthly log. Patients will also maintain daily exercise and diet logs to document their physical activity, and food and beverage consumption for monthly review. The data will be transferred by the project author into an Excel spreadsheet that is organized to fill in the data required, A1C values (November and February) and monthly logs (December, January). An EMR query set for the month of August 2020 will be obtained for a baseline A1C values with current DM care practice. The query process will be repeated in November 2020 and February 2021 for an updated A1C value. Descriptive statistics will be reported as frequencies along with proportions for categorical variables

Deliverables: 1. Project Excel spreadsheet. 2. Presentation of project outcomes to team.

Reference

Jones, B., Vaux, Emma., Olsson-Brown, A. (2019). How to get started in quality improvement *BMJ*; 364: k5408.

APPENDIX D

Patient Consent Form

Study Title: Telemedicine as A Tool to Manage Poorly Controlled Diabetes Mellitus: A Quality Improvement Project

Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-55

Researchers: *Alicia Calzada-Gonzalez*

Faculty Advisor: Dr. Beverly Quaye

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Alicia Calzada. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This research study purpose is to evaluate effectiveness of telemedicine in patients with poorly controlled Diabetes Mellitus Type 2 (DMT2). You are being asked to take part because you have been identified as having uncontrolled DMT2. Taking part in the study will take about 1 visit (15 minutes) by phone each month for four months. You may not take part in this study if you are a minor (under 18 years of age), pregnant or have a mental disability.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to have

- A1C labs to determine blood glucose control in November and February
- Monthly telephone consult visits to discuss logs (blood glucose value, diet, medication, exercise) and plan of action to decrease A1C to near normal levels.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

The potential benefits to you for taking part in this study are: improved blood glucose control

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

The potential risks from taking part in this study is the possibility of low blood sugar values.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

The data for this study are being collected anonymously. The data for this study will be kept confidential to the extent allowed by law. No published results will identify you, and your name will not be associated with the findings. Under certain circumstances, information that identifies you may be released for internal and external reviews of this project.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study? No

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form implies verbal consent:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

APPENDIX E

Electronic Medical Records Smart Phrase/Sample Visit

Patient #9 _____ Baseline A1C 08/2020 (12.1)

Follow up visit 12/2020, 01/2021, 02/02/21

Dates/A1C value: 11/2020 (11.8), 02/2021 (7.9)

Dates/FBG review: 12/2020, (avg values >130), 01/2021, (avg value >130), 02/2021 (avg <130)

Dates/Medication review: 12/2020 (Compliant), 01/21 (Compliant). 08/2020 No meds, 11/2020 Metformin 500mg bid, 12/2020 Metformin 850mg bid, 01/2021 Metformin 1000mg.

Dates/Diet review: 12/2020 (<40% carbohydrate daily intake (CDI)), 01/2021 (<40% CDI)

Dates/Exercise review: 12/2020 (90 min per week), 01/2021 (120 min per week)

Dates of specialty care (Endo/CDE): None

Assessment (significant findings)

Patient with hx of uncontrolled dm

Diagnosis

Uncontrolled dm

Treatment (changes to meds, diet, exercise, BG check or referral)

Continue metformin 1000mg bid, continue < 40% carbs, increase exercise to 150min/week. pt agreeable.

Evaluation-follow up

Patient to schedule virtual check in visit in 1 month for logs and review as discussed. Pt agreeable.